

Betulin-28-acetate from *Capparis sepiaria* L.

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THE isolation of α -amyrin, β -amyrin, taraxasterol, erythrodiol, β -sitosterol, betulin, a triterpene alcohol ($C_{30}H_{48}O$, m.p. 164°) and a compound, $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$, m.p. 223° was reported earlier from the leaves of *Capparis sepiaria*¹. In this presentation we report the isolation and characterisation of yet another triterpenoid, betulin-28-acetate (**1**) besides n-octacosanol, α -amyrin, β -sitosterol and its glucoside from the whole plant. The structure of **1** has been derived on the basis of its 1H and ^{13}C nmr spectral data and also by chemical transformation.

1**Experimental**

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectrum was recorded in KBr, and 1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra at 300.13 MHz and 75.15 MHz respectively, on a Bruker instrument in $CDCl_3$ with TMS as internal standard. Silica gel (Acme; 100–200 mesh) was used for column chromatography.

Coarsely powdered whole plant (3.5 kg) of *C. sepiaria* was defatted with n-hexane and then extracted with EtOAc in the cold. Both the extracts were separately chromatographed over a column of silica gel and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. α -Amyrin, β -sitosterol and n-octacosanol were isolated from the benzene eluates of hexane extract and identified by comparison with authentic samples. $CHCl_3$ -benzene (4:1) eluates of EtOAc extract on concentration afforded a solid which on

rechromatography gave betulin-28-acetate (**1**; 110 mg), m.p. 202–04° (benzene); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400 (hydroxyl), 1725, 1245 (acetate) and 885 cm^{-1} (exomethylene); ^1H nmr δ 0.75, 0.81, 0.95, 0.96, 1.01 (3H, s, each, 5×Me), 1.67 (3H, s, vinylic methyl), 2.06 (3H, s, acetate methyl), 2.43 (1H, m, H-19), 3.19 (1H, dd, J 13.9 and 5.1 Hz, H-3), 3.84 and 4.23 (1H, d, each, J 11 Hz, CH_2OAc) and 4.58 and 4.68 (1H, s, each, exomethylene protons); ^{13}C nmr δ 38.7 (C-1), 27.1 (C-2), 78.9 (C-3), 38.7 (C-4), 55.3 (C-5), 18.3 (C-6), 34.2 (C-7), 40.9 (C-8), 50.4 (C-9), 37.2 (C-10), 20.8 (C-11), 25.2 (C-12), 37.6 (C-13), 42.7 (C-14), 27.4 (C-15), 29.7 (C-16), 46.4 (C-17), 48.8 (C-18), 47.7 (C-19), 150.1 (C-20), 29.6 (C-21), 34.5 (C-22), 27.9 (C-23), 16.1 (C-24), 15.3 (C-25), 16.1 (C-26), 14.8 (C-27), 62.8 (C-28), 109.8 (C-29), 19.1 (C-30), 170.5 and 21.0 (OCOCH_3). EtOAc eluates afforded β -sitosterol 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside identified by comparison with authentic sample.

Results and Discussion

The ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectral data of compound **1**, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$ (from CMR and DEPT), revealed that it is a triterpenoid containing five tertiary methyl groups, a vinylic methyl, a secondary hydroxyl, an acetoxymethyl and a exomethylene group. The compound on acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine formed the corresponding diacetate, m.p. 216–177°. A comparison of ^{13}C nmr spectral data of **1** with those of betulin and its diacetate² further revealed that the data were in complete agreement with the structure of betulin-28-acetate. The ^{13}C nmr spectral data have been completely interpreted and assigned (vide Experimental). The structure was finally confirmed by establishing the identity (m.p., m.m.p. and co-tlc) of the acetylation product of **1** with betulin-3,28-diacetate³ prepared from betulin by acetylation.

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